

www.arseam.com

ASPECT BASED SENTIMENT ANALYSIS IN MALAYALAM

Ms. Anu P C¹, Ms. Athila², Ms. Heera B M³, Ms. Lini K U⁴, Ms. Lilly
Raffy Cheertha⁵

^{1,2,3,4} UG Students, Department of Computer Science and Engineering,

⁵ Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering,
IES College of Engineering, Chittilappilly, Thrissur.

Abstract:

Objective-Our objective is an attempt to do aspect based sentiment analysis in Malayalam. The main problems existing in this domain are there only coarse grained tasks considering only polarity, but not fine grained tasks considering the aspect on which the user is commenting. Although so many works were proposed for universal languages like English, it is less for dialectal Malayalam.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- To develop a movie site which consist of a database contain the whole details of movie. The sentiment words are inputted by the user, the system will generate appropriate response according to the input. Result can be displayed in the form of emotions with emoji's.

Findings- It consist of three sections. Admin consist of whole details of registered users and movie reviews. Admin can login to the movie site and add/remove specified informations. Next, the User login to the movie site, input the review and submit it. The system will generate corresponding output and display the result using emotions and emoji's. Guest, the non registered user can visit the movie site and understand the overall review of the movies.

Limitations- It does not consider a large passage as the input.

Practical implications- This paper is very helpful for those who find sentiment analysis in Malayalam in a movie site.

Originality/Value- This will help to express the emotions in Malayalam terms with emoji's.

Keywords- Natural Language Processing, Sentiment Analysis, Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis, Polarity, Senti-Wordnet.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

The internet holds a considerable amount of user generated content describing the opinions of customers on products and services through blogs, tweets and other social media forms. These reviews are valuable for customers making purchasing decisions and companies guiding business activities. However, browsing the extensive collection of reviews to search for useful information is a time-consuming and tedious task. Consequently, sentiment analysis and opinion mining have attracted significant attention in recent years as they pave the way for automatic analysis of user reviews and the extraction of information most relevant to users.

Sentiment analysis entails several interesting and challenging tasks. One traditional and fundamental task is polarity classification, which determines the overall polarity of a sentence or document. However, these tasks are coarse-grained and cannot provide detailed information, such as the aspects on which the users comment. Recently, there has been a shift towards the fine-grained task, such as aspect-based sentiment analysis, which not only involves analyzing the opinionated text's polarity and intensity, but also identifying the aspect of the opinion.

Natural Language Processing is the ability by which a computer program identifies what a human being has said in the exact context spoken by him. It can be also considered as a field of artificial intelligence. One of the most emerging field of NLP is Sentiment Analysis. It is in short a cognitive process which can extract user's feelings and emotions. In detail it is defined as subjective information extraction by the use of NLP, text analysis and linguistics. it is widely used for a variety of applications which include reviews , social medias for marketing and customer service. It is also otherwise called opinion mining. It can be used to find out whether a film is having a positive or negative review.

1.1.1 Expanding Domain Sentiment Lexicon through Double Propagation

In most sentiment analysis applications, the sentimentlexicon plays a key role. However, it is hard, if not impossible, to collect and maintain a universal sentiment lexicon for all application domains because different words may be used in different domains. The main existing technique extracts such sentiment words from a large domain corpus based on different conjunctions and the idea of sentiment coherency in a sentence. In this paper, we propose a novel propagation approach that exploits the relations between sentiment words and topics or product features that the sentiment words modify, and also sentiment words and product features themselves to extract new sentiment words. As the method propagates information through both sentiment words and features, we call it *double propagation*. The extraction rules are designed based on relations described in dependency trees. A new method is also proposed to assign polarities to newly discovered sentiment words in a domain. Experimental results show that our approach is able to extract a large number of new sentiment words. The polarityassignment method is also effective.

Our work is closely related to which extracts domain specific sentiment words in Japanese text. In their work, they exploit sentiment coherency within sentence and among sentences to extract sentiment candidates and then use a statistical method to determine whether a candidate is correct. However, their idea of selecting candidates restricts the extracted sentiment words only to contexts with known sentiment words (seeds), and the statistical estimation can be unreliable when the occurrences of candidates are infrequent with small corpora. The proposed method identifies domain specific sentiment words from relevant reviews using only some seed sentiment words (we currently focus on product domains). The newly extracted sentiment words and features are utilized to extract new sentiment words and new features which are used again to extract more sentiment words and features. The propagation ends until no more sentiment words or features can be identified. As the process involves propagation through both sentiment words and features, we call the method *double propagation*

1.1.2 Summarization beyond sentence extraction:

A probabilistic approach to sentence compression

When humans produce summaries of documents, they do not simply extract sentences and concatenate them. Rather, they create new sentences that are grammatical, that cohere with one another, and that capture the most salient pieces of information in the original document. Given that large collections of text/abstract pairs are available online, it is now possible to envision algorithms that are trained to mimic this process. In this paper, we focus on sentence compression, a simpler version of this larger challenge. We aim to achieve two goals simultaneously: our compressions should be grammatical, and they should retain the most important pieces of information. These two goals can conflict. We devise both a noisy-channel and a decision-tree approach to the problem, and we evaluate results against manual compressions and a simple baseline.

Most research in automatic summarization has focused on extraction, i.e., on identifying the most important clauses/sentences/paragraphs in texts. However, determining the most important textual segments is only half of what a summarization system needs to do because, in most cases, the simple concatenation of textual segments does not yield coherent outputs. Our goal is also to generate coherent abstracts. However, in contrast with the above work, we intend to eventually use *Abstract*, which are widely available, in order to automatically learn how to rewrite *Texts* as coherent *Abstracts*. In the spirit of the work in the statistical MT community, which is focused on sentence-to-sentence translations, we also decided to focus first on a simpler problem, that of *sentence compression*.

1.1.3 Sentiment Analysis in Multiple Languages: Feature Selection for Opinion Classification in Web Forums

The Internet is frequently used as a medium for exchange of information and opinions, as well as propaganda dissemination. In this study the use of sentiment analysis methodologies is proposed for classification of Web forum opinions in multiple languages. The utility of stylistic and syntactic features is evaluated for sentiment classification of English and Arabic content. Specific feature extraction components are integrated to account for the linguistic characteristics of Arabic. The entropy weighted genetic algorithm (EWGA) is also developed, which is a hybridized genetic algorithm that incorporates the information-gain heuristic for feature selection. EWGA is designed to improve performance and get a better assessment of key features. The proposed features and techniques are evaluated on a benchmark movie review dataset and U.S. and Middle Eastern Web forum postings. The experimental results using EWGA with SVM indicate high performance levels, with accuracies of over 91% on the benchmark dataset as well as the U.S. and Middle Eastern forums.

Stylistic features significantly enhanced performance across all test beds while EWGA also outperformed other feature selection methods, indicating the utility of these features and techniques for document-level classification of sentiments. Analysis of Web content is becoming increasingly important due to augmented communication via computer mediated communication (CMC) Internet sources such as email, Web sites, forums, and chat rooms. The numerous benefits of the Internet and CMC have been coupled with the realization of some vices, including cybercrime. In addition to misuse in the form of deception, identity theft, and the sales and distribution of pirated software, the Internet has also become a popular communication medium and haven for extremist and hate groups.

1.1.4 Opinion Target Extraction Using Word-Based Translation

This paper proposes a novel approach to extract opinion targets based on word based translation model (WTM). At first, we apply WTM in a monolingual scenario to mine the associations between opinion targets and opinion words. Then, a graph based algorithm is exploited to extract opinion targets, where candidate opinion relevance estimated from the mined associations, is incorporated with candidate importance to generate a global measure. By using WTM, our method can capture opinion relations more precisely, especially for long-span relations. In particular, compared with previous syntax-based methods, our method can effectively avoid noises from parsing errors when dealing with informal texts in large Web corpora. By using graph-based algorithm, opinion targets are extracted in a global process, which can effectively alleviate the problem of error propagation in traditional bootstrap-based methods, such as *DoublePropagation*. The experimental results on three real world datasets in different sizes and languages show that our approach is more effective and robust than state-of-art methods.

With the rapid development of e-commerce, most customers express their opinions on various kinds of entities, such as products and services. These reviews not only provide customers with useful information for reference, but also are valuable for merchants to get the feedback from customers and enhance the qualities of their products or services. Therefore, mining opinions from these vast amounts of reviews becomes urgent, and has attracted a lot of attentions from many researchers. In opinion mining, one fundamental problem is opinion target extraction. This task is to extract items which opinions are expressed on. In reviews, opinion targets are usually nouns/noun phrases. For example, in the sentence of “*The phone has a colorful and even amazing screen*”, “*screen*” is an opinion target.

II. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

So many works have been proposed for Sentiment Analysis in Universal Languages like English, although it is comparatively less for Malayalam. Some of the important background papers that contributed to the proposed idea are been discussed here. Mood extraction [3] is a difficult task to refine moods such as happy, sad, angry etc. There are certain words which point to emotional response of a particular situation/object. Sandosham, dhukam are examples. This feature of a word which helps in analyzing sentiment in a particular context is known as semantic orientation. To do this Reference word sets depicting desirable and undesirable response is created manually. POS tagging of words are done and adjectives and adverbs are extracted based on the assumption that they are polarity words. Then compare the words with a reference word set for moods and do necessary semantic orientation calculation. In SentiMa rule based approach has been applied. First of all a data base is created which consists of positive and negative polarity words for Malayalam. The extracted words from the sentence is compared with the database to assign the corresponding polarity, if nothing matches then neutral polarity is given. Negation rule is applied here. Final polarity is calculated by summing up the polarity of each word in the sentence.

DISADVANTAGES

- The main problem is there are coarse grained tasks considering only polarity.
- Although so many works were proposed for universal languages like English.
- Works less in dialectal language like Malayalam.
- Ambiguities and language divergences are more.
- Emoji's are not used

2.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

The most emerging area in NLP now a days is Sentiment Analysis (SA) which is a cognitive process in which the user's feelings and emotions are extracted. It has a variety of applications. It can be used to analyze whether the product review is positive or negative, based on tweets how people respond to ads, bloggers attitude about president changed since election, identifying child suitability of videos based on comments. Although there has been a lot of works published for universal languages like English, works on dialectal languages like Malayalam is comparatively less. But importance of Malayalam is increasing on social medias and shopping sites. This shows the scope of the topic. Another weak point of existing system is that the task done till today is only coarse grained in Malayalam considering only just classification of negative and positive polarity without considering the aspect on which the user is commenting. Such a fine grained task is also considered here most commonly known as Aspect based sentiment analysis. It can contribute to other fields like data mining and web mining.

So we propose Sentiment Analysis in Malayalam. In this the inputted sentence is splitted and compressed. The system will recognize the polarity of the sentence and identifies the emotions of that sentence. After that the result is displayed in terms of emotions and emoji's.

ADVANTAGES

- Emotions expressed in Malayalam terms
- Emoji's and feelings
- Polarity can be checked
- Effective result

III. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION MODELS

3.1 IMPLEMENTATION MODULES

Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis in Malayalam consist of mainly three modules, they are

ADMIN

USER

GUEST

3.1.1 ADMIN

Login

Using a user name and password, the admin can login to the movie site. The movie site contains a preset database and also the admin can access the database.

User details

When we click on the user details button, it gives the details of registered users. Such as user name, address, email id, contact details etc. The admin can add newly registered user details, delete old or unused users, and can block the unwanted users.

Movie Review

It contains the details of movies given by the registered user. This review also giving the information about movie rates generated by the user, ie starring option is also provided.

List

When we click on the list button, it provide mainly three options that is add, remove and modify. Using add option the admin can add movie reviews into the database and also movie reviews can be deleted using remove option. Modify can modifies the appropriate movie reviews.

3.1.2 USER

Register

A user can be a registered user by entering the user details into the appropriate movie site. That is by using user name, address, mail id, and further contact details a user can register to the movie site.

Login

By entering the user name and password , a registered user can login to the movie site.

Movie Review

After login to the movie site, the user can give comments or story details of the movie as the input. Remember that only a registered user can login and entered into the site and can give the input.

Display

Displaying the output as result generated by the system in the form of emotions and emojis.

When the user click the submit button, the movie details saved into the database.

3.1.3 GUEST

A guest may be a non registered user or any other people who can visit the movie site and understand the overall view of appropriate movie reviews

3.2. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The figure represents the Architecture Diagram of Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis in Malayalam. First the user gives movie review as input. The system extract Sentiment sentence and compress it. It recognizes the polarity of

that sentence and identify the emotion of the sentence. Finally the result will be published to users and stored it in data base.

Fig: Architecture Diagram

IV. CONCLUSION

Sentiment analysis is an important area of natural language processing. It has a lot of applications in product and film reviews, social networking sites etc.. it plays a major role in data mining and web mining. The works are very less in dialectal languages like Malayalam even though so many are there for universal languages like English. Even though some of the works exist it doesn't take into consideration fine grained details like the aspect on which the user is commenting otherwise called as aspect based sentiment analysis. This work was an attempt to do aspect based sentiment analysis in Malayalam. The current system can only analyze some of the emotion smileys. This can be extended by analyzing more emotions. Aspect based sentiment analysis helps to improve the quality of the feature on which the author is commenting.

V. REFERENCES

- [1] Deepu S.Nair, Jisha P. Jayan, Rajeev R. R, Elizabeth Sherly, "SentiMa-Sentiment Extraction for Malayalam", 2014.
- [2] <https://www.python.org/about/getting started>.
- [3] Neethu Mohandas, Janardhanan p s nair, "domain specific sentence level mood extraction from Malayalam text", international conferences on advances in computing and communication 2012.
- [4] Text book of opinion mining and sentiment.
- [5] www.programiz.com/python programming.